

SUMMARY REPORT OF WORKSHOP ON TRAINING RESOURCE METADATA TESTBED

Wednesday 19 January 2022, 15:00 - 16:30 UTC (held via Zoom)

Organised by: FAIRsFAIR

Report prepared by Elizabeth Newbold based on the collective notes taken on the day. With thanks to the participants and co-organisers Angus Whyte and Andre Vieira.

About the workshop:

The workshop was organised by the [FAIRsFAIR](#) initiative as a follow up to an earlier meeting held in April 2021¹ on harmonising training resource metadata for EOSC Communities. This workshop explored the issues further based on work undertaken by FAIRsFAIR on a testbed of metadata for training resources. The workshop engaged the InfraEOSC-5 projects ([EOSC-Pillar](#), [ESOC-synergy](#), [NI4OS-Europe](#), [ExPaNDs](#)) as well as representation from related ESFRI Cluster Projects ([PaNOSC](#), [SSHOC](#), [ENVRI-FAIR](#), [EOSC-Life](#) - including [ELIXR TeSS](#)), [EOSC Future](#) and other related initiatives ([RDA-IG ETHRD](#), [OpenAIRE](#)).

The workshop goals were three fold:

- to discuss the feasibility/extent to which the [RDA ETHRD IG](#) minimal metadata elements in the EOSC landscape based on the testbed findings
- to feedback any issues identified by the workshop to the RDA ETHRD IG on the application of the metadata set
- to discuss and present the use of the Dublin Core Tabular Application Profile method for representing Metadata Application Profiles

Agenda:

15:00 Welcome Introduction to the testbed approach and analysis	Elizabeth Newbold, Angus Whyte, FAIRsFAIR
15:15 Open discussion on analysis and discussion points	All
<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Mandatory elements: Should all elements be mandatory, or should there be an element of flexibility?● Clarification/changes to metadata elements terms/definitions	

¹ Newbold, Elizabeth, Kayumbi, Gabin, Whyte, Angus, & Lazzeri, Emma. (2021). Summary Report: Workshop on Harmonising Training Resource Metadata for EOSC Communities. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4769468>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Should controlled vocabularies be more strongly recommended? 	
15:55 Dublin Core Tabular Application Profile	Nancy Hoebelheinrich, RDA ETHRD IG metadata focus group lead
16:10 EOSC Future Catalogue Developments	Venkat Shanmugasundaram, EOSC Future
16: 30 Close	
Background documents information: Discussion document on metadata testbed RDA minimal metadata data dictionary	

Training Resources Metadata Testbed Analysis and Approach:

Elizabeth Newbold and Angus Whyte from the FAIRsFAIR project set out the work that had been done on a testbed of resources drawn from multiple communities of established catalogues (as well as resources that were not yet catalogued) to assess the application of the RDA ETHRD IG minimal metadata. The aim of the testbed was to:

- Identify issues to report on regarding harmonisation to inform future work e.g EOSC Future catalogue developments
- Explore how the minimal metadata set may be used to demonstrate improved discoverability
- Make recommendations for action based on analysis of the materials/metadata provided.

The issues identified related to:

- Whether all elements should be mandatory or if more flexibility is required
- Clarification/changes to metadata elements terms/definitions specifically for:
 - Access Costs
 - Learning resource type
 - Authors
 - Primary language
 - Version date
- Whether controlled vocabularies should be more strongly recommended.

The introductory presentation was followed by a discussion session the main points of which are recorded below.

Dublin Core Tabular Application Profile:

Nancy Hoebelheinrich (Knowledge Motifs LLC) is the lead for the work on minimal metadata in the RDA ETHRD IG. Nancy presented the work that the group has been undertaken working on a Dublin Core Tabular Application Profile (DC-TAP)² and how it can be applied to the minimal metadata set.

² [DCMI: DC Tabular Application Profiles \(DC TAP\) - Primer \(dublincore.org\)](#)

The potential benefits of using DC-TAP approach are that it can help to determine the correct usage of a metadata scheme by:

- Defining the properties used to describe resources, using terms from published namespaces
- Stating constraints applicable to the values of metadata properties
- Describing the rules that govern the creation and reuse of the metadata

Nancy outlined the main issues that make the DC-TAP approach potentially useful as a machine-readable representation of the RDA minimal set:

- Many catalogues are in use by different stakeholders
- Many different schemas are already used in these catalogues
- Interest in finding a metadata profile based on existing schemas, for different platforms to adopt

The overall benefit would be the potential for easier metadata exchange among service providers, repositories and portals.

A draft of the DC-TAP is [available](#).

EOSC Future:

Venkat Shanmugasundaram (OpenAire/EOSC Future) gave a brief outline of the direction the EOSC Future training resource catalogue is progressing, the metadata schema that is in development (based on the RDA ETHRD-IG minimal metadata recommendations) and the rules of participation. Information is available on the [EOSC Future wiki](#).

Discussion:

The workshop had three topics for discussion based on the testbed analysis and a further discussion point on the use of the Dublin core Tabular Application Profile.

Topic 1: Should all elements be mandatory, or should there be an element of flexibility?

The RDA-IG ETHRD minimal metadata set recommends that all elements are mandatory, however it is clear that whilst the majority of the elements are already in use in training resource catalogues they are not all used and not all are mandatory. The menti poll indicated that there was a strong feeling that there should be some flexibility in the recommendation that all elements are mandatory.

Should all the elements be mandatory or should there be some flexibility?

If you think there should be flexibility which elements do NOT need to be mandatory?

description	Free text options	version date
Learning outcome	constraints	persistent identifiers for the learning resource
access costs	Access cost	Learning outcomes; PIDs

If you think there should be flexibility which elements do NOT need to be mandatory?

Learning Outcome	versioning	free text items
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Almost all. A resource providers should be well guided to provide as much as possible, but making very few tags mandatory.

Whilst the results of the mentimeter would imply that there was a strong consensus on the need for flexibility with the metadata recommendations, the discussion was much more nuanced.

Specifically, the metadata would be much richer if all the elements were included and “null” values used rather than not including the metadata element. This would improve the quality of the information being provided generally, something that it was felt had been rather overlooked in previous discussions.

The discussion reflected that whilst difficult it would be important to keep learning outcomes as a mandatory element as it is so valuable for learning resources and so infrequently used, this would help to encourage more uptake, and that training materials are much more reusable if this information is provided.

Ultimately it was agreed that for any service provider there is tension between completeness/quality of metadata and maximising the quantity of records included. One approach is to set the bar in favour of quantity first and raise the quality over time working with the producer/providers to encourage and improve the quality of metadata whilst also maintaining a balance between setting the level too high that it discourages participation or is too resource intensive to be sustainable.

Topic 2: Clarification/changes to metadata elements terms/definitions

The test bed analysis highlighted some specific questions for some of the metadata elements.

- Learning resource type - the data dictionary had this as a non repeatable element however examples showed that there were times when more than one had been applied. This may depend on the controlled vocabulary used or the level of granularity of the catalogue but it

was agreed that this should be reported back to the RDA group for consideration and possible explanation to be included in the data dictionary.

- Authors - when reviewing materials especially videos and materials on learning platforms, there is a potential problem in determining the author of the materials. For example the presenter of the materials in a specific event may be different from the author and this is not always clear. The discussion considered whether the term 'contributor' could be considered. Due to time constraints this issue wasn't fully explored but it was agreed that this needs further consideration.
- Access Costs - this was not a widely used term already and when analysing resources there were other issues not related to costs that need to be considered. There was a general agreement that access costs are too narrow and that a wider term relating to constraints or restrictions could be more useful which would then have included costs. The action was to report this back to the RDA group for consideration.
- Primary language - the definition provided was felt to be somewhat confusing and could be simplified to be the language of the version being catalogued and that other language versions would have a separate record.
- Version date - the description associated with version date is fairly complex and in discussion it was agreed to suggest to the RDA group that this be simplified.

The discussion provided an opportunity to share understanding of how terms are currently or could be applied and where further guidance or clarity is required. The lack of definition of granularity of the metadata description is an issue particularly affecting the first two points above, e.g. course materials may have multiple authors for different modules, and use multiple resource types.

Topic 3: Should controlled vocabularies be more strongly recommended?

The third topic for consideration was related to the recommendations for controlled vocabularies. Angus Whyte led the discussion, highlighting that the discussion within the RDA group hadn't reached a mature state. Given the broad scope of the RDA group it could only provide examples rather than recommendations. In the EOSC context there is a possibility of a more authoritative position.

The discussion on controlled vocabularies concentrated on three elements where there is most need for guidance:

- Target Audience
- Learning Resource Types
- Learning Outcomes

One of the key challenges for controlled vocabulary guidance is the need to accommodate those that are already in use across different domains.

The discussion on target audience considered whether the [EOSC Actors from the SRIA](#) would be a possible starting point - but it was clear that not all audiences are included in this and that whilst having an EOSC slant on the target audience would potentially be too narrow. However it was thought that within the EOSC ecosystem it would be a good opportunity to explore the creation of a controlled vocabulary for this aspect, working in an inclusive and collaborative way, looking at what is already in use and where roles are missing.

One of the proposed controlled vocabularies for learning resource types is the [LMRI](#)³ and specifically the [LRMI “concepts scheme”](#) which is ongoing work. Whilst there was no discussion it was agreed that this is an area that needs further consideration in the EOSC Future project and needs to take account of the learning path concept which is being piloted in TeSS and also being considered in the Ni4OS project.

The final discussion point related to learning outcomes where there is currently no recommended controlled vocabulary and when included in a catalogue record tends to be narrative in the description or as uncontrolled keywords. Again there was no immediate solution whilst terminology like terms4FAIRskills has some potential it is challenging to encompass everything relevant given the diverse nature of materials. Another suggestion would be to consider [Blooms taxonomy](#)⁴ to provide a list of verbs that could be used.

The discussion was wide ranging, with many suggestions and agreement that these are aspects that need further work that could be taken forward by the INFRAEOSC-5 projects training and skills taskforce in collaboration with EOSC Future and the RDA ETHRD IG.

Topic 4: Use of the Dublin Core Tabular Application Profile?

The work on the development of the DC-TAP was well received by the workshop participants with the potential benefits as being something that would be useful to explore in the EOSC context. There was some discussion that whilst the spreadsheet approach is a good way to collaboratively build a machine actionable metadata application profile, that there needs to be further discussion of how to apply this in the EOSC context, e.g. to make recommendations regarding the semantic equivalence of terms drawn from the base schemas (e.g. bioschemas, LOM) and the serialisation formats to be used to enable catalogues to expose their metadata and have it harvested by the core EOSC catalogue..

Next steps:

Following the workshop the discussion and testbed analysis was shared with the RDA ETHRD IG for further consideration.

³ [DCMI: About LRMI™ \(dublincore.org\)](#)

⁴ [Bloom's taxonomy - Wikipedia](#)